

Proposal of a new method to monitor the loss of workability and setting of mortars

M. Pułtorak^{1}, T. Russo¹, J. Granja¹, P. B. Lourenco¹ and M. Azenha¹*

¹ ISISE, ARISE, University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, 4800-058 Guimarães Portugal

Abstract. Workability loss in mortars refers to a reduction in the material's ease of handling, placing, and finishing during construction. It indicates a decrease in the plasticity or the ability of the material to be easily moulded or shaped. Setting refers to the process by which the mortar transitions from a plastic, workable state to a hardened, rigid state. This setting process is crucial in construction and masonry work, where mortars are commonly used to bind together bricks, stones, or other building materials. In the scope of testing of mortar, workable life of mortar can be assessed according to EN 1015-9. Existing standardized methods for testing fresh properties of mortars are destructive, not continuous and generally insufficient. This work proposes a device for non-destructive testing and continuous monitoring of the evolution of resonant frequency of a bar embedded in the mortar mixture to be tested at the fresh state.

Introduction

Cement-based materials like mortars change significantly the properties during the fresh state. A few methods exist for measuring those properties over time, and most of them are destructive. Most of the testing methods for assessing fresh properties of mortars are described in the set of standards EN 1015. There are methods for assessing the consistency by flow table (EN 1015-3) or plunger penetration (EN 1015-4), air content by EN 1015-7, and bulk density of fresh mortar according to EN 1015-6. Considering the methods for assessing the setting of mortars or workability loss, the standardized methods are limited to penetration resistance according to ASTM C403, or workable life by EN 1015-9. Apart from those methods there are others related to cementitious pastes using Vicat needle according to EN 196-3 or ASTM C191. All of the mentioned methods are using the discrete testing times and the targeted value is interpolated, when intending to get information about ages at which testing was not conducted. There are also methods based on ultrasonic waves and electrical resistivity but their sensitivity at the very early ages is often limited. Therefore, there is a scarcity in the continuous monitoring of fresh properties of mortars in first hours where the material. In this work, a method is proposed for continuous monitoring of the fresh properties of mortar related to the changes that occur at the very early ages before setting, so that workability loss up to setting can be monitored.

Developments and main results

In the method proposed herein, the mortar is examined through modal identification of a bar which is fixed to the bottom of the mould with the fresh mortar to be tested inside. The bar pultrudes outside of the specimen and an accelerometer is fixed to its extremity. The loss of workability up to setting and even further stiffening can be detected by the increase in the resonance frequency of the bar. The scheme of the measuring system with the mould and sample inside can be seen below in Figure 1a. Due to mixing, compacting, and connecting the samples to the device, each test starts 15 minutes after time zero, which is when the dry

* Corresponding author: monika.pultorak@civil.uminho.pt

constituents first contact water. The mould for the test was printed 3D using PLA material. The sample of the mortar inside has dimensions of 40x40x40mm. The steel bar is fixed to the bottom of the mould by bolts. The steel bar has dimensions of 10x137x2mm. On the top of the bar the accelerometers are fixed by bolts.

For the first pilot tests, a ready-mix dry multipurpose mortar SECILtek REDUR Multi was used. The information about the setting time of the material, as reported by the manufacturer as occurring between 3 and 5 hours. The ready-mix dry mortar and water for mixing were stored in a climatic room with a stable temperature of $20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Two batches of mortar were made in two consecutive days. Each batch consisted of 2000g of dry mortar and 240 g of water giving two specimens for testing. Each specimen is labelled as Specimen Day.SampleNo. The batches were prepared with the same regime of mixing and compacting.

Fig. 1 a) Scheme of the test with sample dimensions b) Results of the frequency evolution of four specimens

The device used to monitor the vibrations of the bar has been thoroughly described in the literature. As can be seen in Figure 1b the evolution of the frequencies is significant. The range between the frequencies at the beginning and at the end of the test is equal to 57,4 Hz. Up to the end of the marked setting (5h) the evolution is increasing fast and after 5 hour the frequencies are slowly reaching the flattering of the results around 12 hour of testing At 1 hour of testing the CoV is equal to 4,45%. At 4 hours, which is in the middle of the setting time range, the CoV is 1.06%. At the end, the CoV is 0.72%, which is below one percent, so the spread of the result is minimal.

Conclusions

This work presents a testing method of continuous monitoring of the properties in fresh state of material before setting time, through monitoring of the resonance frequency of an embedded steel bar. This evolution of the frequencies is visible and significant. Those changes inside the material are connected to the mechanical behaviour of the change of the material and supposedly can be connected to setting or workability loss. The change is detected much earlier than the methods which are already existing in the literature. The range of frequencies is sufficiently great to observe the changes inside the material. Nevertheless, further experiments must be conducted to explain the change in frequencies, which are already in progress.

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